

The development of literature in England and Uzbekistan in the 19 century

Mukumova Nozima Ulug'bek qizi

Bachelor's, student

National University of Uzbekistan

Mukumovanozima19@gmail.com

+998990043110

Annotation. This study is devoted to the study of literature of the 19th century in America and Uzbekistan. Laying the foundation and forming new directions. The work presents the works of famous writers and the work of creating novels.

Аннотация. Данное исследование посвящено изучению литературы 19 века в америке и Узбекистане. Заложению фундамента и формированию новых направлений. В работе представлены работы известных писателей и труд создания романов.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot 19-asr Amerika va O'zbekiston adabiyotini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Poydevor qo'yish va yangi yo'nalishlarni shakllantirish. Asar mashhur yozuvchilarning asarlari va romanlar yaratish ishlarini taqdim etadi.

Key words: romanticism, revolution, jaddism, progressive-democratic wing, social and political themes

Ключевые слова: романтизм, революция, джаддизм, прогрессивно-демократическое крыло, социальные и политические темы

Kalit so'zlar: romantism, revolutsiya, jadidchilik, progressiv demokratik qanot, ijtimoiy va siyosiy mavzular

The development of world literature in the 19th century, when the foundation of its

state originality was laid, was distinguished by a number of features that have retained their significance to this day. These features are largely associated with American Romanticism.

Romanism found a special role in the USA: it arrived in the country, thanks to which it took its place among the literary sources of the world.

In the early colonial period and in the Premises of Enlightenment, the significance of the congress of literature was in general subordination to the USA. American writers often went beyond the borders of Europe, primarily England, in their work, but they themselves did not turn out to be researchers of the course of literary development in other countries. Coup lost romance: environment with Irving, Cooper, Edgar Allan Poe, US literature has become an active factor in the international artistic process.

Romanticism dominated the United States for a very long time. It remained the leading artistic method until the end of the Civil War between North and South in 1865. The highest achievements of the greatest writers of that time are associated with it: Irving, Cooper, Emerson, Thoreau, Edgar Poe, Hawthorne, Melville, Whitman, and others.

It was no coincidence that Fenimore Cooper first gained recognition with the release of the novel *The Spy* (1821), where the events of the American Revolution are covered with a haze of heroic legend glorifying the rebel leader George Washington and obscure patriots who lay down their lives at the altar of Liberty.

The closer connection between American romanticism and the Enlightenment is explained by the peculiarities of the American Revolution, in which the democratic forces managed to win more tangible victories than in the French one (the revolution in the USA did not lead to the creation of a Napoleonic-type dictatorship, did not include the consequences of restoration, etc.) . In addition, the American Revolution was inseparable from the Revolutionary War; it meant not only the

victory of the bourgeois system over the feudal system, but also the liberation of the country from colonial rule. This further raised and strengthened the authority of the enlighteners, who acted as the "founding fathers" of the American Republic.

At the same time, anti-enlightenment pathos was also strongly inherent in romanticism, the components of which are well known: skepticism in relation to the possibilities of the human mind, craving for the irrational, mystical, the cult of intuition, the denial of the idea of "common good", "social contract", putting forward in opposition this idea of the idea of the eternal enmity of man and society, of a lonely person, towering like an inert crowd and challenging the whole world, etc. To replace the enlightenment concept of the original perfection of human nature, romanticism brought the idea of a split personality, a splitting of consciousness. Part of the Romantics paid a generous tribute to the idealization of the Middle Ages - an era that, from the point of view of the Enlightenment, was exceptionally unreasonable.

Printing in America, starting from the reconstruction period, was also clearly oriented to two layers, one might say, two classes of readers. Large centers of book sales - New York, Boston and Philadelphia supplied products for educated citizens to bookstores, while "subscription" publishers provided books that carried "culture" to small towns and villages in America. A huge, mostly competent, but not too refined readership: artisans, farmers and members of their families - pre-ordered the publication of books on history, moral issues, medical care, patriotic or humorous compositions, and only occasionally artwork.

In this regard, the creative fate of Kate Chopin (1851-1904), a talented prose writer, a strong master of the novelistic genre and "local color", who won reader recognition with two collections of stories from the life of Louisiana Creoles "Old-timers Bayo" (1894) and "A Night in Acadia" is very indicative. (1897). The writer was literally destroyed by criticism and subjected to public ostracism after the publication of the

novel "Awakening" (1899), a psychologically subtle and masterly study of the female soul.

At the beginning of the 20th century, a national enlightenment movement, Jadidism, was born. One of the leaders of the Turkestan Jadids was Munavvar Kary Abdurashidkhanov (1878-1931), an Uzbek educator and head of the Shura-i-Islam organization in Turkestan. S. Abdugaffarov was the first native Turkestani who mastered the Russian language, a Muslim educator. In the early 1880s, Abdugafarov, one of the first representatives of the local intelligentsia, came to the conclusion that it was necessary to modernize the structure of the traditional education of the younger generation (while maintaining the system of Islamic values). Another educator from Tashkent was A. Avloni, who in 1904 became one of the leaders of the Jadids, and in 1909 he created the organization "Zhamiyati Khayratiya". In 1907, Avloni founded the Shukhrat newspaper. Avloni was the first to offer to teach geography, chemistry, astronomy and physics in the national schools of Turkestan.

The Tashkent reformer, Ismail Obidi (1880-1941) began publishing the Jadid newspaper "Tarakki" in Uzbek in 1906, but the newspaper was soon closed by the authorities due to a number of critical articles. In Tashkent he became known as Ismail Tarakki. Another native of Tashkent was Abdurakhman Sadyk oqli (1879-1918), a prominent Uzbek educator, polyglot translator, journalist, Jadidist. In 1908 he met Munavvarkary Abdurashidkhanov, through whom he got acquainted with the ideas of Jadidism. In 1915, he opened the socio-political journal Al-Islah, which was closed by the authorities in 1918 due to critical articles. The editor of the magazine was Abdurakhman Sadyk oqli himself. He wrote a number of works on Islamic ethics and on the history of Muslim holy cities. A native of Tashkent was the first Uzbek lawyer U. Asadullahodzhaev, one of the founders of the Turan society (1913). He founded the newspaper "Sadoi Turkiston" in Tashkent (April 4, 1914) and was its editor. He was the chairman of the Shura-i Islamiya

society. Secretary and member of the Central Council of Muslims of Turkestan, created at the First

Congress of Muslim Muslims of Turkestan (April 1917). Member of the Central Committee of the All-Russian Muslim Council (1917).

The literature of the first half of the 19th century was headed by the poets Mohammed Sharif Gulkhani, Makhmur, Agakhi and others. Gulkhani's work "Tales about the Owl, or Sayings", which was written in the form of a folk tale based on the book "Birds' Conversation", where the author criticized the immorality of the courtiers, feudal lords -rulers and reactionary clergy. The poetic heritage of the poet Munis Khorezmi (1778-1829) became a masterpiece of classical literature. He owns the works "Treatise on Literacy" (1804), as well as the historical work "The Garden of Happiness" (unfinished); this work was completed in turn by Agakhi, who also left the sofa "Talisman of Lovers". The representatives of the progressive-democratic wing of Uzbek literature were the poets Zavki, Mukimi, Zakirjan Furkat, Dilshad, Otar-ogly, Avaz and Anbar Atyn, who laid the foundation for a realistic reflection of reality and introduced social and political themes into literature.

References

Абдумавлянов А., Бабаханов А., История узбекской литературы, Таш., 1966:

История узбекской советской литературы, М., 1967;

Licey.net

Students-library.com